

Exploring the search for home and belonging. Search engines as players on the property market

Jessica Enevold Duncan^a, Ann-Sofie Klareld^b

^a Lund University, Helgonavägen 3, Lund, 223 62, Sweden

^b Lund University, Helgonavägen 3, Lund, 223 62, Sweden

1. Introduction

With this presentation we aim to open a discussion on the influence of search engines in relation to the property market. Here we view them metaphorically as players, without assigning them any proactive value, that is we cannot say for sure what effects they actually have. We explore them, due to their prevalence in everyday life, their potential “societal influence” (Lewandowski, 2023) and relevance for the always so controversial property market. *Hemnet.se* (<http://www.hemnet.se>) is the world’s biggest digital property market, if measured in terms of number of searches per capita in Sweden (Enevold Duncan, 2024). However, people’s window-shopping and actual shopping for homes on Hemnet (Hemnet, 2025), scoping out dream homes, precariously living out their house dreams (Enevold Duncan 2024), is not our primary focus here. We focus on a type of secondary search generated by these kinds of property foraging, when prospective buyers or curious consumers want to know more: where is a certain property is located? What is the address? Who is selling?

We have followed two different urban areas, in two different towns, picked originally from eye-catching depictions in media (*Expressen*, 2021, Ranby, 2015) Agnes i Lund, 2024, Kulturportalen, 2019, SVT, 2024, *Sydsvenskan*, 2021) and archives (Ek, 1982, Hyresgästföreningen, 2024)– where one is generally described as more affluent, safe and trendy, the other as unsafe and in crisis. We have found two properties for sale in these areas and followed them from their advertisement on *Hemnet.se* and *Boneo.se* (<https://www.boneo.se>) another digital site for searching properties in Sweden, on to *hitta.se*, a prominent contact information-search engine in Sweden [literal translation: Find.se]. Our examples represent two very different residential areas, the location of which are not only presented, but also its presumed inhabitants, who are on an aggregate level, statistically profiled and forefronted on *hitta.se*.

The search engine offers its home-seekers not only phone numbers and addresses, but also maps, and information about ‘lifestyles’ – presented in text as well as images. In our presentation we indicate that *hitta.se* through this data generation, defines and circumscribes urban areas in ways that may actually “produce” them as more or less desirable real-estate objects, potentially indirectly influencing the property market, and how areas are perceived and thus bought and sold and understood in people’s everyday home-making.

Hitta.se uses open data in combination with data from commercial sources. Open data has been described as “an extension of the principle of public access to information” (Internetstiftelsen, n.d.) and is closely connected to public archives, which are an important part of society’s knowledge infrastructure (Trace, 2022). *Hitta.se* and other search engines, such as *mrkoll.se* (<https://mrkoll.se>), can do this, because public agencies should make their public data available for reuse in innovations based on digital information, simultaneously contributing to increased transparency in public administration (Government Offices of Sweden, 2022).

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EMAIL: jessica.enevold@kultur.lu.se (A. 1); ann-sofie.klareld@kultur.lu.se (A. 2)

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0874-6651> (A. 1); <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6342-0393> (A. 2)

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Departing from our two examples “Hospitalsgatan in Nöden” and “Vougts väg in Rosengård” we imagine how presumptive homeowners looking for a house or condominium in these areas first find their homes on *Hemnet* or *Boneo*, or other site, but then consult for example the *hitta.se*-search engine when considering if a particular area is for them or not, if it is worth investing in: if they can identify with or profit from it in some way. *Hitta.se* uses open data to present information about average income, loan-to-value ratio, and which political parties its inhabitants vote for. With this comes lifestyle-related information derived with the aid of a household-based consumer segmentation model called Mosaic by the company Experian, (<https://www.experian.com/>).

When data from public sources are combined with this other type of information and presented as ‘demographic’ facts they tell a very specific story of imagined inhabitants, their hobbies and homes and of each area that defines its place in the respective city which can be illustrated by the presentations of common interests in the respective area. Following Wendy Chun (2021), the presentations of the search-engines consulted can be understood as contributing cultural encodings, mediating certain world-views and inhabitants. This means search-engines are not neutral but deliver “discrimination data” potentially emphasising certain biases in terms of class and race for example (Chun, 2021).

Figure 1: Vougts väg. The heading above the image says: “Young and middle-aged low-income families with children in multicultural suburban areas of a big city”.

Hitta.se also provides photo montages that illustrate the inhabitants of a search object. These, too, are there as reference data, for the prospective buyer to ‘process’ and decide: do I belong here or not, can I identify with this or not, do I relate to this or not? Similar to the “you are what you eat” assumption, the characterization “you are where you live” can be applied to your life choices, and resulting (perceived and projected) status and life styles, as dwellings are highly connected to humans’ propensity for categorizing the world socioculturally, which we by now understand is far-reaching and actually never neutral (see for example Bowker and Star, 1999).

Figure 2: Hospitalsgatan. The heading above the image says: “Young middle-income earners in condominiums in established suburban areas outside major cities”.

2. Concluding remarks

In this presentation we assume that prospective home-makers search for a flat or house that will reflect them. *Hemnet* and *Boneo* provide real-estate ads as sources of storytelling indicating the socioeconomic position among people living in specific areas. A search engine like *hitta.se* tells similar but different stories, combining open data with other information sources. As we stated above, we may conclude that *hitta.se* through its data generation, defines and circumscribes urban areas in ways that may actually “produce” them as more or less desirable real-estate objects, potentially indirectly influencing the property market, how areas are perceived and thus bought and sold and understood in people’s everyday home-making. We call attention to how this both contributes to cementing some areas as ‘good’ and some as ‘bad’, thereby in various ways influencing the labelling and consequent status of dwelling areas and people, real-estate prices and potentially in the long run, demographics and gentrification processes. In short, search-engines may be interpreted as players on the locally and globally so significant property market.

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